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Financial Analysis of Tapped Rubber Productivity and Tapped Rubber Wood Potency by Clone GT1 and Seedling in Sarolangun Subdistrict of Jambi, Indonesia

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Abstract

Generally, a part of forest area in Sarolangun had been used by people, especially for farming and planting activities. If the area was not driven to the real policy, it would impact to the transformation of forest area function to be gardening and farming or other economic activities. The Society tapped rubber Forest must be driven to enlarge the forest usage for wood industries and to create the job vacancy. The main purposes of this research were (1) to study financially the effort of Society Plantation Forest of tapped rubber and non tapped rubber trees. (2) to get a perspective of Society Plantation Forest development in monoculture pattern for tapped and non tapped rubber Based on the financial analysis of Net Present Value (NPV), Net B/C and IRR at interest rate of 5%, the effort of tapped rubber had a value of Rp.299,061,000; 7.54 and 26.3% respectively. The effort of non tapped rubber had a negative value of Rp.36,982,000; 0.59 and unworthy bussiness. The annual average value of income and the effort scale of tapped rubber was Rp.16,473,487 and 3 hectares respectively. From the research results, it could be suggested that: (1) for the non tapped rubber effort it should be better if the people select seedlings from a clone that could make the wood quality better to obtain the higher selling price. (2) it was suggested that in the year before the rubber trees produce latex, it should be better to plant the area with agricultural crops and vegetables to optimize the land usage and to provide added value to the farmers.

Keywords: Financial, Produktivity, Tapper Forest Planting, Sarolangun

PRELIMINARY

Community rubber plantation forests or what was commonly called rubber agroforestry on ex-swidden land, generally from seedling/grain planting material for wood production, had long been used by local residents as the main crop for reforestation activities. The step towards developing rubber plantations from planting material for superior seeds or clones to produce latex was an advancement for rubber farmers to increase sap productivity. Both were state assets that had various benefits for life, namely in the form of direct benefits that were felt and indirect benefits. Community rubber forests and rubber plantations were also a resource that could provide goods and services for community and state needs. Therefore, the processing of smallholder rubber forests and rubber plantations in an area had made forests and plantations the main resources for economic development. Processing of forests or plantations could had a positive impact on economic development, including increasing foreign exchange, absorbing labor, and encouraging regional development and economic growth (Santoso, 2008).

Traditionally, most of the community rubber plantations in Sarolangun were built through a slash-slash-and-burn system from both secondary and old rubber forests. The rubber plants from seedling / sweeping seeds were planted irregularly with high density. Then, during the first two to three years food crops were intercropped. Garden management was carried out extensively, with minimal weeding without significant fertilization so that various former secondary forest vegetation grows naturally together with

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rubber trees. This condition caused the pattern of rubber gardens to resemble forests dominated by rubber plants, so that this system was also known as 'rubber forest'.

Community rubber plantations were rubber plantations in production forests built by individuals to increase the potential and quality of production forests by applying silviculture to ensure the sustainability of forest resources (Anonymous 2007).

Sarolangun District had a forest product processing industry with a total installed capacity of 95,700 m³/year. If the existing industry yields an average of 60%, then the minimum required raw material for logs was 133,960 m³/year. Meanwhile, based on statistical records, the production of logs in Sarolangun Regency in the last three years had decreased, respectively, reaching 92,7773.98 m³, 41,311.51 m³, and 48,485.06 m³. There was a raw material deficit of almost 40,000 m³ - 90,000 m³ each year, thus considering the high demand for wood raw materials, the supply of community rubber forests was expected to meet these needs (Anonymous 2008).

In an effort to develop community rubber forests, cultivate and develop production as well as the mechanism for trading system for community rubber forest plantations, it was necessary to be optimally organized and directed with certainty in production and a marketing system that provided a value of hope for the community, it was necessary to disseminate it to the community with the support of the local government and related agencies that were expected. all investments invested in the development of community rubber forests and future rubber plantations would be more.

Community rubber forest development areas generally use agroforestry systems for all types of woody forest plants. The majority of smallholder rubber forest farmers choose the type of rubber plant in the development of plantation and plantation forest programs in Sarolangun Regency.

From the above description, the authors were interested in examining in depth through which financial criteria were more feasible than the two types of rubber planting material.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Location and Time Research

This research was conducted in Singkut District and Bathin VIII District, Sarolangun District, Jambi Province. The objects used in this study were rubber forest areas and smallholder rubber plantations in the Sarolangun Regency area, namely: Rubber stands without tapping / wood production (planting material for seedling / sweeping seeds and rubber stands for tapping / producing latex (clone GT1).

Research Data

Sources of data in this study were based on primary data and secondary data. The financial analysis included data related to financing such as fixed costs and variable costs tabulated in cost groups, while the output components in the form of wood and non-wood production during productive plants at the end of the cycle were tabulated in the yield group. The price used was the price in effect at the time of the research. Furthermore, a financial feasibility analysis was carried out at an interest rate of 5%.

Data Analysis

The financial feasibility of community rubber forests in Sarolangun Regency would be analyzed using several investment criteria (Kadariah, 1986) as follows:

- 1) Payback Period (PP)
- 2) Net Present Value (NPV)
- 3) Benefit-Cost Ratio (Net Benefit Cost Ratio/Net B/C)
- 4) Internal Rate of Return (IRR)
- 5) Value of Money that could be Paid Each Year (Equivalent Annual Annuity / EAA)

a. Payback Period (PP). This analysis was used to determine the investment period that had been issued from the profits earned by a project.

$$PP = n_1 + (n_2 - n_1) \left[\frac{a_1}{\{ a_1 + a_2 \}} \right]$$

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- n₁: The last year, where the cumulative net benefit was negative
- n₂: The year, when the accumulative net benefit was positive
- a₁: The accumulative value of the net benefit was negative (at n₁)
- a₂: The accumulative value of the net benefit was negative (at n₂)

Net Present Value (NPV), was a calculation method to find out the present value of the difference between profits and costs at a certain discount rate and could show an excess of profits compared to costs incurred, with the following formulation:

$$NPV = \sum_{t=0}^{t=n} \frac{Bt - Ct}{(1 + i)^t}$$

Notes: Benefit in year t (Bt), Costs in year t (Ct), Applicable interest rate (i) and The length of the time period (n)

This criterion was if the NPV > 0, it means that the business was profitable. Conversely, if the NPV < 0, the business was not feasible, and if NPV = 0, then there was a break event point, meaning neither profit nor loss.

- a. Net Benefit Cost Ratio (Net B / C), was a method to describe how many times the profit was obtained from the costs incurred. This method also shows the ratio of the sum of the present value of the profits to the total present cost value, calculated by the following formula:

$$\text{Net B/C} = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^{t=n} \frac{B_t - C_t}{(1 + i)^t}}{\sum_{t=1}^{t=n} \frac{B_t - C_t}{(1 + i)^t}} \begin{matrix} \longrightarrow & Bt - Ct > 0 \\ \longrightarrow & Bt - Ct < 0 \end{matrix}$$

With the criteria if the value of the Net B / C ratio > 1, then the business was declared feasible to operate and vice versa if the net B / C ratio < 1 then the business was not feasible to operate.

- b. Internal rate of return (IRR), indicating the maximum interest rate that a business could pay or in other words, the ability to earn income from invested money, IRR was calculated by the formula:

$$IRR = i_1 + \frac{NPV^+}{NPV^+ - NPV^-} (i_2 - i_1)$$

Notes: The first discount factor (interest rate) where the NPV was positive (i₁), Second Discount Factor (interest rate) where the NPV was negative (i₂).

- c. Equivalent Annual Annuity (EAA), shows how much money could be paid each year with the same amount, calculated by the formulation:

$$EAA = NPV \times \frac{i}{1 - (1 + i)^{-n}}$$

Notes: Interest rate (i), The length of the time period (n).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In Sarolangun district, a small part of the community had used superior seed planting material, one of the GT 1 clones, which had long been cultivated as an early generation. Therefore, based on the highest production data in each sub-district in Sarolangun Regency, it was stated that Singkut Subdistrict was the highest sap productivity compared to other sub-districts which only reached figures below 1 ton KK / ha / year.

Table 1. Data on Latex Production and Productivity in Sarolangun District

No	Sub District	Wides Area (ha)		Production (Ton)	Productivity (kg/ha)	Farmer
		TBM	TM			

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1	Batang Asai	2.460	3.639	2.900	797	1.989
2	Limun	2.712	1.928	1.878	974	3.453
3	Sarolangun	2.895	4.437	3.989	899	2.718
4	Pauh	7.139	10.088	9.069	899	2.402
5	Pelawan	3.257	5.607	5.489	979	4.546
6	Singkut	1.255	8.429	9.533	1.131	3.601
7	Mandiingin	12.108	9.989	8.930	894	5.809
8	Air Hitam	1.350	2.350	2.289	974	3.132
9	Bathin VIII	6.518	11.574	10.984	949	4.762
10	CNG	1.483	1.680	1.497	891	2.505
Total		41.177	59.721	56.558	947	34.914

Potential of Wood-Producing Rubber Stands (Seedling Seeds)

The spacing of the rubber trees producing agroforestry systems was generally irregular, but in this study we describe the spacing of 7 x 3 m or 480 trees per hectare. During the age of 3 years to 25 years, the death rate was as much as 40%. These deaths were due to the quality of planting materials and plant diseases. The production of rubber plants could be tabulated as follows:

Table 2. Production of Rubber Plants Without Tapping

Ages	n	d	h	TV	MAI	CAI
3	432	15,0	8,5	48,6	16,21	
5	380	20,3	10,6	84,7	16,94	18,03
12	350	33,5	11,5	212,8	17,73	18,29
25	300	49,0	14,6	454	18,16	18,56
30	250	55,0	16,6	492,6	16,42	7,74

Notes: individual tree (n), Total Volume (TV), Mean Annual Incremeant (MAI), Current Annual Incremeant (CAI), (d) diameter (cm) and (h) height (m).

In Table 2, it could be seen that thinning and mortality show an increase in diameter increment and volume increment until age 12 years and after age 12 years thinning had less effect on annual increment (MAI) for standing stock. This shows that the average MAI increment for standing stock of rubber trees without tapping at the age of 25 to 30 years had decreased from 18.1616 m³ / ha to 16.42 m³ / ha. Thinning was carried out from the age of 3 years, where every year about 10% of rubber plants without tapping were reduced until the 12th year, with the aim of obtaining optimal increment production. Graphically, the seedling of the rubber plant was shown in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1. Graph of Relationship of Increment and Age of Rubber Without Tapping (Data from Table 1) From Figure 1 it could be explained that the intersection of MAI and CAI at the age of 25 shows an optimal increment in the 25th year, but the business continued until the age of 30 years because it was not financially profitable. The optimal increment was 18.16 m³ / ha at the age of 25 years with a diameter of 49 cm

Production of GT Clone Rubber Plants 1

Rubber plants could be tapped around the age of 7 years or a diameter of over 20 cm until the age of 25 years. The production of rubber latex (latex) could be explained in Table 3.

Table 3. Rubber Latex Production (kg / ha)

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Ages to	Production Results (kg/ha)	AP	MP
7	3.780	540	
8	4.320	540	540
9	4.870	541	550
10	5.425	543	555
11	5.985	544	560
12	6.550	546	565
13	7.120	548	570
14	7.700	550	580
15	8.400	560	700
16	9.050	566	650
17	8.500	500	-550
18	7.900	439	-600
19	7.200	379	-700
20	6.400	320	-800
21	5.500	262	-900
22	4.450	202	1050
23	3.250	141	1200
24	1.950	81	1300
25	600	24	1350

Notes: Annual average production (AP) and The annual average production increase was running (MP).

Table 3 could be explained, that the age of 7 years rubber could be tapped with a total production of 3,780 kg. Until the age of 16, the production of rubber sap had increased with a total production of 9,050 kg and after the age of 16, the production of rubber latex had decreased until the age of 25 years. The trend of increasing rubber latex production from the age of 7 to 16 years shows a linear increase. There were several reasons why the maximum production was reached in the 16th year, including the 16th year, which was the last year of tapping on virgin skin, after that year, renewable bark had been tapped. This was also according to Siregar (1995), that the latex vessels increase according to the age of the plant and the maximum production of rubber was achieved when the plants were 15-17 years old. The relationship between rubber latex production and age could be seen in the figure below:

Figure 2. Graph of Rubber Latex Production (Data from Table 2)

In Figure 2, it could be seen that the average latex production from the age of 7 to 16 years shows an increase, as well as the average annual increase of latex. After the age of 16 years, the average production of latex had decreased significantly, while the increase in the average annual production of latex had decreased to a negative number. This means that optimal production could only be achieved at the age of 16 years and after that production had decreased, but financially they could still generate income.

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If it was compared between the increment of rubber tapped and the increment of rubber that was not tapped, it turns out that the increment of rubber tapped was smaller than the increment of rubber that was not tapped. Therefore, the increment growth was slower than that of untapped rubber. The production volume of tapped rubber increment could be seen in Table 3 below.

Table 4. Production volume of tapped rubber increment

Ages	n	d	h	TV	MAI	CAI
5	456	15,0	10,0	60,4	12,1	
10	433	22,5	12,2	136,5	13,6	15,2
12	412	25,5	13,3	167,8	13,9	15,7
14	400	28,7	14,1	200,6	14,3	16,4
18	371	35,6	14,2	262	14,6	15,4
22	360	39,2	14,4	281,3	12,8	4,8
25	350	41,9	15,0	289,5	11,6	2,7

Notes: individual tree (n), Total Volume (TV), Mean Annual Incremeant (MAI), Current Annual Incremeant (CAI), (d) diameter (cm) and (h) height (m).

Tapped rubber had an MAI increment for standing stock from 5 years to 18 years of age and the optimal increment was 14.7 m³ / ha at the age of 20, after which the increment decreased at the age of 25. Decrease in stand population from 5 years to 25 years of age by 20-30% due to mortality and thinning treatment. In general, the incremental relationship could be seen in the graph below.

Figure 3. Grape of Tapped Rubber Increments (Data from Table 3)

Rubber Plant Business Income

Rubber trees could be tapped from the age of 7 to 25 years and with a selling price of IDR 10,000/kg. The amount of income from rubber latex harvesting was shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Total Tapping Rubber Business Income

Ages to	Production Results (kg/ha)	Unit Price (Rp)	Benefit (Rp)
7	3.780	10.000	37.800.000
8	4.320	10.000	43.200.000
9	4.870	10.000	48.700.000
10	5.425	10.000	54.250.000
11	5.985	10.000	59.850.000
12	6.550	10.000	65.500.000
13	7.120	10.000	71.200.000
14	7.700	10.000	77.000.000
15	8.400	10.000	84.000.000
16	9.050	10.000	90.500.000
17	8.500	10.000	85.000.000
18	7.900	10.000	79.000.000
19	7.200	10.000	72.000.000
20	6.400	10.000	64.000.000

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21	5.500	10.000	55.000.000
22	4.450	10.000	44.500.000
23	3.250	10.000	32.500.000
24	1.950	10.000	19.500.000
25	600	10.000	6.000.000

Based on Table 5, it could be explained that at the age of 7 to 16 years there was an increase in income from Rp. 37,800,000 to Rp. 90,500,000 and after 16 to 25 years it had decreased. The reduced production of rubber also affects the amount of income, because income was also reduced as shown in the table above.

In rubber without tapping, the wood-producing income came from thinning, intermediate harvest and final harvest. In the 12th year, rubber without tapping for wood produced an income of Rp. 19,170.00; harvest between Rp. 77,180,000 and the final harvest of Rp. 122,250,000.

Financial Analysis

The costs involved in exploiting the community rubber forest in Sarolangun District include fixed costs and variable costs. Fixed costs include land and building taxes and wages for workers' salaries, while variable costs include planning costs, land preparation costs, provision of seeds and their transportation, planting, embroidery, weeding, thinning, maintenance, building guard huts, purchasing fertilizers and equipment and harvesting costs.

The details of the costs required for land management in each stand had a different cycle as in the attachment. The investment value for each community rubber forest concession and plantation varies and depends on the type of stand to be cultivated. The investment value for each stand could be seen in Table 6.

Table 6. Investment value of community rubber forest concession

No.	Standing Trees	Investation Value (Rp)
1.	Tapping rubber (clone GT1) which produced latex	51.719.000
2.	Rubber without tapping for wood (Seedling seeds)	70.519.000

Based on Table 6, it could be explained that the exploitation of rubber tapped from the GT 1 clone planting material required the smallest investment when compared to rubber without tapping which produced wood from seedling / sweeping seed planting material. This was because the tapped rubber had the shortest cycle / rotation compared to the non-tapping rubber stands cultivated by farmers, so that it quickly produced yields. In addition, the type of rubber that was tapped could produce sap that could be harvested every year.

In the process of financial analysis, actual current values are used based on the rupiah with the US Dollar indicator in effect at the time of the research because the US Dollar value was assumed to be stable against the rupiah value.

According to price information from PT Kirana Windu in Jambi, the price of rubber latex was IDR 10,000 / kg; The price of rubber wood according to PT GNL which operated in Batang Hari, Jambi Province was IDR 320,000 / m³. Based on the above prices, the selling price of each stand could be determined by taking into account risk factors and safety factors.

Financial Analysis of GT Clone Exploitation 1

The initial investment in tapping rubber for latex production was Rp. 51,719,000, while the total cost for the entire rubber cultivation activity for 25 years was Rp. 336,709,000 and the gross income was Rp. 1,089,500,000, so the business had a beneficial value (B / C Ratio) of 3.1.

Latex latex production could be harvested from 6 to 25 years of age and reach optimal production at 16 years of age as shown in Table 2 and calculated financially at an interest rate of 5%, resulting in a Net Present Value (NPV) and Net B / C of Rp. 299,061,000 and 7,54. This interest rate simulation was still feasible up to an interest rate of 15%. This statement was strengthened by the analysis of the Internal Rate of Return (IRR) model with a value of 26.3%. If a farmer borrows money from the bank for Rp.10,500,000 with a loan interest rate of 8% and in installments for 5 years, paid from the age of 8 years, then the installment amount was Rp. 7,160,000. The results above indicate that tapped rubber stands at an interest rate of 5-15% were feasible to cultivate because their value was positive and was greater than the Minimum Acceptability Rate (MAR = 5%).

Financial analysis of timber producing rubber (seedling seeds)

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The initial investment in rubber cultivation without tapping for wood was Rp. 70,519,000, while the total cost for the entire planting of rubber without tapping for 30 years was Rp. 152,376,000 and the gross income was Rp. 219,600,000, so the business had a beneficial value. (B / C Ratio) of 1.4.

Rubber wood production could be harvested from the age of 12 years at 213 m³ as a thinning harvest, while the age of 25 years had a wood production of 454 m³ with a selling price of Rp. 300,000 / m³, and the final harvest at the age of 30 years with a production of 493 m³ as Data in Table 1 and calculated financially that at an interest rate of 5%, the Net Present Value (NPV) and Net B/C values are negative IDR 36,982,000 and 0.59. This shows that at an interest rate of 5%, the rubber business that was not tapped was not feasible to run. The above results indicate that a rubber stand that was not tapped at an interest rate of 5% was not feasible to cultivate because its value was negative and was smaller than the Minimum Acceptability Rate (MAR = 5%). In general, the financial analysis of plantation forest exploitation could be seen in Table 7.

Table 7. Recapitulation of plantation forest exploitation financial analysis

No	Standing trees	PP (year)	NPV (Rp.)	Net B/C	IRR (%)
1	Tapping rubber (clon GT 1)	8,1	299.061.000	7,54	26,3
2.	Wood production rubber	29,5	(-) 36.982.000	0,59	0

Based on Table 7, it could be explained that the exploitation of tapping rubber plants from GT 1 clone planting material at a factor discount rate of 5-10% was feasible to be cultivated according to the age cycle, while rubber that was not tapped / wood producer was not economically feasible because of its value. The NPV was negative and the Net B / C was less than 1, which means that the business was not feasible to operate and the respective financial indicators were as written in table 7. Of the two stand exploitation, it turns out that planting rubber tapping clones GT 1 was the most feasible to operate because had the most feasible financial value from the types of stands mentioned above, namely the fastest return on capital between the two and the IRR level was above 20%, the rubber tapped by the GT 1 clone type was quite feasible to be recommended to farmers to be cultivated in Sarolangun Regency while rubber that was not tapped was not suitable for recommendation to farmers because it did not bring k profit (loss) when valued financially.

However, community rubber forest from rubber trees without tapping / producing wood was one of the rubber-based agroforestry systems (RAS). Economically, the productivity of smallholder rubber gardens was low, but ecologically, smallholder rubber gardens were very rich in biodiversity. Extensive rubber management by farmers was based on the resources (labor and land availability) and the funds they have.

Rubber Plantation Business Scale

The exploitation of smallholder rubber plantations in Sarolangun District was inseparable from the area of land that the farmers were trying to cultivate. This land area was related to the business scale. Business scale was a comparison between the total consumption expenditure of each farmer family / year and the annual average income (Equivalent Annual Annuity). In one farmer family it was assumed that it consists of 5 family members with the consumption expenditure of each farmer family head / year of Rp.50,000,000/family/year, so the scale of the business to cultivate the area of the farmer's land could be seen in Table 8.

Table 8. Scale of Plantation Forest Exploitation Business

No	Standing rubber	Rotation (year)	Planting distance (m)	Location	EAA Rp	Effort Scale (ha)
1	Latecs production rubber	25	7x3	Jambi	16.973.487	3

Based on Table 8, it could be explained that the rubber plant stands of GT1 planting material had a profitable business scale for rubber farmers. Tapped rubber had a business scale of 3 ha with a rotation of 25 years. Meanwhile, rubber that was not tapped for wood production was not feasible to work on because it shows negative results financially so it did not had a business scale.

CONCLUSION

The potential (total volume and increment) of rubber that was not tapped at 30 years of age rotation was 454 m³ and the MAI increment for standing stock was 18.16 m³ / ha, while rubber tapped in a 25-year rotation was 262 m³ with MAI increments. for a standing stock was 14.56 m³ / ha.

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Based on the financial analysis of Net Present Value (NPV), Net B/C and IRR at an interest rate of 5%, tapped rubber, respectively, had a value of Rp. 299,061,000; 7.54 and 26.3%, and 11.8%, while non-tapping rubber had negative values of 36,982,000; 0.59 and not worth the effort.

The value of the annual average income (EAA) and the business scale of rubber tapping to produce latex was Rp. 16,473,487 with a business scale of 3 ha.

Exploitation of tapped rubber required a smaller area of land. Rubber without tapping was not feasible to work with because it shows negative results financially, so it did not had a business scale.

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